

Identifying Latent Drivers of the Money Supply - GDP Contribution Relationship in the Construction Industry.

Jeffery Osayande Guobadia¹, Ifiok Enobong Mfon² and Ngozi Christiana Eduzor³

¹Department of Building University of Uyo, Nigeria. jeff.guobadia@gmail.com

²Department of Architecture University of Uyo, Nigeria. ifiokifiokifiok@gmail.com

³Department of Business Administration, University of Uyo, ngozieduzor9@gmail.com

Abstract

The relationship between money supply and the construction sector's contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria has become a subject of heightened attention. While an increase in money supply can potentially lead to positive economic outcomes, including credit availability, heightened consumer spending, and increased investments, challenges such as inflation, central bank interventions, and external risks introduce complexities. The construction industry, a vital player in the economic landscape, significantly contributes to GDP through infrastructure projects, job creation, and economic diversification. However, challenges within the construction sector, such as economic cycles, environmental concerns, labour exploitation, and safety issues, add layers of complexity. Despite recognizing the impact of money supply on economic indicators, establishing a clear correlation between "Money Supply" and "Contribution to GDP" within the construction industry remains elusive. Various factors, including project timelines, material dependencies, labour costs, regulatory hurdles, and the influence of government policies and corruption, contribute to this ambiguity. In the context of developing countries like Nigeria, where the relationship's clarity is uncertain, policymakers face challenges in steering economic growth. This study aims to uncover the hidden factors shaping the link between money supply and the construction sector's contribution to Nigeria's GDP, providing insights for policymakers, stakeholders, and scholars. It is meant to guide effective policy formulation and enhance the construction industry's contribution to national economic growth by addressing inefficiencies, delays, and corruption.

Keywords: Money Supply, GDP Contribution, Construction Industry, Nigeria, Monetary Policy, Economic Growth.

Introduction

The relationship between money supply and economic growth has become a focal point in recent times within the field of monetary economics (Ogunmugiwa and Ekone, 2010; El-seoud, 2014). This heightened attention is attributed to the crucial role of economic growth among the macro-economic goals of nations, both developed and developing. The relationship between money supply and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) involves a multitude of factors that contribute to the complexity of this economic dynamic. As noted by Bara and Mudzingiri (2016), an increase in the money stock can lead to a chain reaction of positive economic outcomes, including the availability of credit, increased consumer spending, and higher investments, ultimately resulting in GDP growth. However, this relationship is far from linear, as factors such as inflation, interventions by central banks, and external risks introduce nuances and challenges. One notable challenge is the timing speed associated with the effects of changes in money supply. Time lags and the influence of external factors, such as corruption and unfavourable government policies, contribute to a discrepancy between the timing of changes in money supply and their real-time impact on the economy (Oliva et al., 2022). Consequently, the correlation between money supply levels and GDP growth rates may vary, depending on the interplay of these complex factors.

The construction sector emerges as a significant player in this intricate economic landscape. According to Toms, Wilson, and Wright (2020), monetary policy interventions, particularly in the construction sector, are

contingency-based and focus on factors related to business ideas, especially in construction. This sector has a substantial impact on national economies, directly contributing to GDP through the construction of residential and commercial buildings, roads, and other infrastructure elements. Additionally, the construction industry generates employment for various professionals, including engineers, architects, and construction workers, creating a ripple effect on related industries such as steel manufacturing, cement works, and professional services (Zhang et al., 2018). However, challenges and sustainability concerns within the construction industry, such as economic cycles, environmental implications, labour exploitation, safety problems, and unskilled employees (Juricic et al., 2021), introduce complexities. These challenges underscore the importance of ethical, environmentally-friendly, and inclusive sustainable economic growth within the construction sector.

Despite the recognized impact of money supply on economic indicators, a clear correlation between "Money Supply" and "Contribution to GDP" within the construction industry remains elusive. Guobadia et al. (2024) reveal a weaker correlation, emphasizing that while money supply influences specific economic metrics, its overall impact on the construction industry's contribution to GDP is uncertain. Various factors contribute to this ambiguity, including project timelines, material dependencies, labour costs, regulatory hurdles, and the influence of government policies and corruption (Yap et al., 2019; Ugochukwu et al., 2017). In the context of developing countries like Nigeria, where the relationship between money supply, construction sector contribution to GDP, and the ensuing impact on economic growth is unclear, policymakers face challenges in guiding the economy toward growth. The lack of clarity may also deter private investors, potentially hindering the nation's economic progress. This study seeks to address this anomaly by exploring the mediating factors that shape the link between money supply and the construction sector's contribution to Nigeria's GDP.

The aim of this study is to uncover and analyze the hidden factors that determine the relationship between money supply and the construction industry's share of GDP. It aims to achieve this by identifying these mediating factors and evaluating their impact on the growth of Nigeria's construction sector. The Significance of this lies in its ability to reveal underlying forces that extend beyond conventional factors, offering insights for future studies and guiding policymakers in refining monetary policies and formulating sector-specific interventions. By addressing inefficiencies, delays, and corruption, the study aims to contribute to increased allocation efficiency and enhance the construction industry's contribution to national economic growth. The study aims to provide informed information to policymakers, business stakeholders, and scholars, guiding them in formulating effective policies that comprehend the intricate dynamics of this nexus.

2.0 Literature Review

The dynamics between money supply and GDP are quite intricate, especially for the effects of construction sector in relation to factors such as inflation, monetary multiplier, long term economic patterns, investment resources, and technological progress, among others. In truth, as reflected in the observation of Guobadia *et al.* (2024), money supply growth can be affected by factors such velocity of money, investment efficiency and resource limitations among others rather than being equal at all times. In the short-run, authorities may rely on changes in money supply aimed at stimulating economic activity including in recessions through quantitative easing. Yet, these underlying threats persist today including oversupply, inflation failure of uneven distribution and integration into world economy inputs. Risks and uncertainties affect the construction sector, and it is equally important for project managers, contractors, policymakers, and investors to understand what drives different factors (Larsen *et al.*, 2016). Through discovering latent forces, stakeholders can enhance the efficiency and efficacy of projects by locating bottlenecks and mitigating safety hazards. In the realm of contemporary organizational dynamics, the influence of leadership styles on both employee engagement and overall business success stands as a critical area of inquiry (Eduzor, 2024) While transformational leadership has been theoretically championed for its ability to inspire and motivate, empirical examinations of its concrete impact on employee engagement and business outcomes remain somewhat limited. This research aims to address this gap by delving into the intricacies of transformational leadership and its implications for organizational performance. This means better resource management, reduced waste generation and cost optimization as well as efficiency in project time lines (Langenwalter, 2020).

Recognition of secret factors, the ability to address market tendencies and investors' confidence as well as society laws, allows stakeholders to invest in projects, thus, contributing more successfully (Bergman and Foxon, 2020). Policymakers can use these buried drivers to combat industrial challenges like worker shortages and

sustainability related issues in their policies or strategic activities. The analysis of the driving forces behind material prices, supply chain disruptions and economic swings enables construction players not only to mitigate risks but also adapt strategies for favourable market environment.

2.1 Money Supply and GDP Contribution in the Construction Industry

The money supply measurement of the construction industry has changed over time, and initial attempts were to use broad monetary aggregates. But these approaches do not take into account the specificity of financing instruments and liquid dynamics in this sphere (Chiang et al., 2015). The historical development of GDP contribution to the construction industry reveals large fluctuations resulting from wider economic trends, policy decisions, and conditions specifics (Alaloulet et al., 2021). Major findings include sustaining growth, boom and busts cycles, regional distinctions influence of policies. To succeed, policymakers and investors must have the necessary knowledge of historical trends to make informed decisions about future developments in the building industry (Hampson et al., 2014).

The critical events in the evolution of this nexus are financialization construction, changes to central bank policies, government spending initiatives and supply chain disruptors and technological advancements. According to Storm (2018), financialization has improved credit access, securities of construction loans and also caused the creation of new financing instruments that may result in positive outputs but end up as asset bubbles and financial crisis. The reactions to policy undertaken by the central banks such as alterations in interest rates and quantitative easing influence construction financing costs alongside overall investments (Davis and Kim, 2015). As it creates liquidity in the construction area, government spending promotes activity and stimulates GDP growth. Events such as pandemics and resource shortages occur on a global level, affecting construction supply chains leading to material costs changes and project timelines (Guttman, 2017). Innovations in construction materials, technologies, and automation may improve resource allocation efficiency while changing dependence on conventional financing approaches.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The construction sector's GDP contribution has evolved over time due to macroeconomic factors, policies, and internal dynamics within sectors. Historical trends indicate continuous increases, amplitude of boom-and-bust waves, geographic disparities, and impacts from policies (Khan et al., 2014). Gomber et al. (2018) stated that financialization of construction, Ifiok Mfonet et al.,(2024) the imperative for sustainable development has catalyzed a global shift towards environmentally responsible practices across various industries. Recognizing the pivotal role of industrial buildings in economic activities, there is a growing need to scrutinize and reform construction methodologies and materials that traditionally contribute to environmental degradation central bank monetary policy adjustments, government expenditure interventions, and monitoring chain disturbances have influenced regulation and the supply money solicitation relationship. Government spending injects money into the building industry, creating activity and GDP increase (Larsen et al., 2016). Global events like pandemics affect the construction supply chain, and materials availability issues spiral effect costs. Mechanization technology's arrival brings implications that demand reconsideration of material viability (Alaloulet et al., 2021). Technological developments and innovative ideas have far-reaching implications, affecting resource dependencies and funding efficiency in the construction industry. Informed decision-making in the complex world economy requires continuous study of impacting components. Variability in the construction sector's GDP share over the past century is due to urbanization, infrastructure development, and living standards improvement (Sahoo and Sethi, 2022). Geographical differences are noticeable, with emerging economies having greater proportions due to rapid development, while developed ones may demonstrate smaller contributions due to slower population growth and increasing prominence of the service sector.

Despite the highly debated causal manner in which money supply affects GDP contribution, however this is one of the relationships that must be sustained to have some reason for running an economy (Okaforet et al., 2016). The money supply is argued as the total cash and other assets value for recording within economy while GDP refers to inboundary valuation of all final goods or services produced using output-based information during a period (Assa, 2016). For the short term, M1s slight hike would allow an economic boom with borrowing and consumption on top of responding inflows for investments driving growth in GDP. Alternatively, if the growth of money supply increases goes overboard it will result to inflation which repudiates any benefits that may have emanated due increase in GDP (Larsen et al.,2016). However, although this bond is not so fluid in the short term,

it creates necessary infrastructures such as roads, contracting platforms to connect bridges and other structures that support human beings to live comfortably like power plants, communication networks among others; this helps the populations consecrate their lives since they can be able to move from one place to another thus leading easily (Weimer and Vining, 2017). Trade also is made possible with building of integrated sectors where people have areas for buying commodities. This is brought about by advanced infrastructure that promises the foreign investors, tourism as well and consequently uplifting of everyday citizens in terms of quality life (Oláh *et al.*, 2018). The industry directly helps in GDP growth by adding to the total value of products and services produced, increasing demand for other materials used items equipment enhancing various sectors. The multiplier effect yet accentuates the economic outcome, since revenue earned by construction sectors is spent in other sector, ultimately resulting into such chain of development (Rüßmann *et al.*, 2015). The Industrial Revolution of the construction industry is ongoing, adopting new technologies such as automation and robotics to build up information modelling (BIM), saving efficiency productivity safety. Project costs reduce timelines.

Figure 2.1. Conceptual Framework of the Study (Researcher, 2024)

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Monetarist Theory

Monetarist theory is a useful analytical framework for analyzing the relationship between money supply and construction's contribution to Nigeria GDP, implying that a positive relationship exists between money supply (M) and real GDP(Q) (Kipkirui, 2014). An expansion in M is likely to stimulate economic activity, which may benefit the construction sector through rates reductions, increased aggregate demand, and possible inflationary pressures (Lagoset *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, it is important to appreciate the built-in limitations of the Monetarist model and look for hidden factors that may affect this relationship. The connection between the level of money supply and construction in Nigeria might be mediated by several factors. However, financial sector frictions including inefficiencies of the banking system or lack of access to credit can slow down money injection into construction investment (Molavi, 2014). Regardless of money supply changes, the institutional setting – as represented by regulative practices, corruption, and political instability – can also have a large impact on construction activities. Moreover, limitations related to input and labour availability, inadequate infrastructure and reputation predisposition for particular forms of construction may act as hurdles restricting the construction sector even with increased investments (Kipkirui, 2014).

2.3.2 Institution Theory

Institutional theory posits that both formal and informal institutions comprising of government regulations, norms, routines and practices play a critical role in economic activity (Fuenfschilling and Truffer, 2014). Nigerian construction, with its variegated environment insulated from stimuli like monetary policy and material costs helps highlight latent forces behind the industry's growth path via an approach stemming on institutional theory (David, 2014). Construction activity is highly affected by formal institutions such as government regulations and policies. Death of growth due to approval processes taking time, administrative red tape and patchy enforcement. More so, there exist, various legal structures that influence investor confidence and project financing, such as contract enforcement, mechanisms of property rights protection, as well as dispute resolution systems (Peters, 2022). In addition, weaknesses in such institutional factors may lead to uncertainties and prevent investment.

Ifiok and Luna (2023) buildings, characterized by their large-scale operations and specialized functionalities, represent a substantial portion of this sector. Their construction and operation demand a reimagining of traditional approaches to align with the urgent imperative of sustainability. Industrial buildings are instrumental

in housing manufacturing processes, distribution centres, and logistical hubs, playing a pivotal role in global supply chains. Yet, their sheer scale and resource-intensive requirements have historically contributed to environmental degradation. The construction industry dynamics are also shaped by financial institutions. The availability of financing mechanism such as mortgages and construction loans are essential for making projects progressive (Cornelissen *et al.*, 2015). The lack of capital, especially for the small and medium companies can form a bottleneck to industry development. Construction industry dynamics are also influenced by informal institutions such as social networks, relationships culture and values (Wang *et al.*, 2018). They can influence the access to contracts, resources and permits producing very uneven playing fields that make market competition unfair. Risk-taking, innovation and long-term planning tendencies show cultural implications that influence decisions for investment performance and project management (Rigtering *et al.*, 2015). The incidence of corruptions, bribery and other informal practices in resource allocation led to higher cost estimates which can discourage formal investment inflows into the construction sector. Therefore, the hidden forces that affect growth in Nigeria's construction sector can only be understood through an institutionalist approach (David, 2014).

2.4 Empirical Review

The study by Zaman *et al.* (2022), focused on determining the hidden driving forces behind Nigeria's contribution to GDP in the construction sector, especially between Critical Delay Factors (CDFs), and Leadership Self-Efficiency (LSE), as well as Transnational Mega Construction Projects (TMCP) success. The research shows that CDFs have a strong negative impact on the success of TMCP while LSE positively moderates this relationship. This implies that key delays, such as corruption, and unfavourable government policies, have the potential to cause significant setbacks for construction projects. The study by Chan and Owusu (2022) details how corruption impacts the relationship between GDP and Contribution of Construction Industry to Economy. It shows that potential corruption can change this link, misappropriating resources and impacting the growth of given sector. It is driven by personal greed, lack of sanctions, political interventions and weak supervisions.

Fiscal policy variables impact on the contribution of construction to Nigeria's GDP, as investigated by Ojo *et al.* (2023), as well as Guobadia *et al.* (2024), implies that government policies such as deficit financing, public spending and institutional effectiveness, have no direct effect on the construction sector, particularly in its contribution to the national GDP. Although the study further analyses the effects of these factors on private investment in construction, it stated that government policies especially with respect to public expenditure, may have an inclination on the allocation of resources, infrastructure growth and project viability, hence, indirectly shaping the construction sector. It also throws light on the role of political economy, technological diffusion and human capital in making construction growth.

As inclined by Guobadia *et al.* (2024), the construction industry in Nigeria is one of the most significant sectors in Nigeria, and by extension, Africa, furthering economic development along with modernization. As the largest employer of construction labour, accounting for 15% of all employees, it has more than twelve million employees. Despite the plausible features of the sector, it is plagued with corruption. Corruption, as suggested by Kolawole (2015), leads to project abandonment, inflated pricing, poor quality jobs, poor workmanship, low labour productivity, and extravagance of resources, and sometimes project collapse, causing fatal injuries, loss of livelihoods, money, time, and death. It spans various platforms, from planning stage to design phase, tendering procedure, construction operation, and maintenance. Corruption, according to Adindu *et al.* (2020), can be both overt and covert, including bribery in planning, permit processing, and failure to meet deadlines for project delivery timings, compromising quality standards or lowering supervision, and so on.

The work of Olanipekun and Saka (2019) shows a mutually dependent relationship between the policies adopted by government concerning growth rate for construction industry in Nigeria. The direct impacts are construction-related activities and immediate policy adjustments in the government sector such as public infrastructure projects, spending programmes, housing plan, along with tax incentive programme. Akaeze and Akaeze (2017) suggested that policies contribute to economic stability, business sentiments and regulatory frameworks helping the construction sector in Nigeria achieve GDP growth.

3.0 Methodology

The construction industry is regarded as a vital source of GDP in Nigeria with an addition between 7-10 percent to its value. It is an important factor for the infrastructural spending, job generation and economic diversification (Babatunde *et al.*, 2018). Nonetheless, it has a set of problems that include uncertain growth and the use of oil revenues not well financed, making finance accessibility one of the greatest challenges for most construction companies, especially SMEs (Tengan *et al.*, 2016). Although, through reserve requirements, interest rates, and open market operations, the Central Bank of Nigeria maintains monetary policy. However, GDP growth in this sector has been erratic due to price shocks on oil prices, local security issues, as well as fluctuations of the global economy (Davis and Kim, 2015). This part is recognized as a key area under diversification programs for non-oil growth, whereby falling productivity rates coupled with corruption and infrastructure issues pose challenges towards continuous economic progress, thus affecting the sectors of the economy including the construction sector (Cornelissen *et al.*, 2015). Unknown latent drivers include the government policies that influence construction activity, informal labour in constructions with positive implications for traditional economic models, corruptions costs and investments, as well disruptive technological innovations which change how productivity is achieved or GDP constructed.

3.2 Research Design

This study will uncover underlying drivers accessible that are inevitably linked with the Monetary Supply GDP Contribution in Nigeria's construction industry. A mixed method design will be used with qualitative and quantitative methodologies that together create the balance to serve as a more holistic representation of the dynamics involved between 2015 and 2022 (Morse, 2016). The qualitative stage will involve a detailed document analysis of some key policy documents and selected economic reports as well as other relevant statements by third parties with knowledge about relationships between global events such constitutional laws or historical stages which then impact development dynamics of the construction sector (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017). The quantitative set in this section will entail data acquisition and analysis to establish the effects that are hidden with regard to drivers on the money supply-GDP contribution nexus and overall growth of Nigeria's construction industry. Therefore, numerical data will be narrowed down from previous studies, publications, policy documents and economic reports in the process using keywords that express the inclinations of this study (Halcomb and Hickman, 2015). The harnessed data will be evaluated using frequency distribution as well as multiple regression frameworks. The following data will be sourced:

1. Construction sector policies of the government such as infrastructure development plans, housing programmes and procurement systems.
2. Money supply trends to the construction sector between 2015 and 2022
3. Corruption perception index in the construction sector between 2015 and 2022

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis of Findings

Budgetary Allocation (Money Supply) to the Construction Sector between 2015 and 2022

Year	Budget (₦' Billion)	3-Year Average
2015	22.9	-
2016	456.96	344.52
2017	553.71	564.54
2018	682.96	554.90
2019	428.03	475.52
2020	315.56	367.43
2021	358.71	385.41
2022	481.97	-

Source: Author's compilation of various NBS reports between 2015 and 2022

Corruption Perception Index

Year	Nigeria's CPI Score	3-Year Average
2015	28	-
2016	27	27.67
2017	28	27.33
2018	27	27.00
2019	26	26.00
2020	25	25.00
2021	24	24.33
2022	24	-

Source: Author's compilation from Transparency International

Conclusion

The complex relationship that can be found between money supply for GDP in this construction industry discloses a complicated mixture of multiple factors. Bara and Mudzingiri (2016) stress that the increase in money supply could result to credit flexibility, more investments and high consumption which can lead into economic growth for a country. But this is not a process without its challenges, as inflationary pressures and central bank interventions along with their consequences on asset prices contribute to the complexity of that relationship. As empirical examples, the historical picture of synchronicity between money stock and GDP growth has been highly diverse. Monetary policy interventions in the sector of construction are more or less contingency-based, while they have a direct and indirect impact on national economies. Onat *et al.* (2020; 19) recognized that much of the GDP is contributed by construction through different infrastructure elements, employment opportunities and spillover effects on related industries.

However, it has many positive features that include economic cycles environmental implications labour exploitation safety issues and unskilled employees. Realizing these obstacles is essential for promoting ethical, environmentally conscious and sustainable economic development. Interestingly, Guobadia *et al.* (2019) focus on a new finding that shows less money supply and an even weaker correlation between the construction industry's contribution to GDP. To this end, the following factors contribute to weakening and hence have an ambiguous link between money supply and overall GDP in this sector. These include project timelines, material dependences among others. The relationship between the money supply and GDP in construction is characterized by a variety of factors such as inflation, monetary multiplier, long-term cyclical patterns, investment resources and technological innovations. Authorities may use changes in money supply for more immediate economic stimulus, although certain immanent threats remain as oversupply; uneven distribution and global integration. It is therefore necessary to look at risks and uncertainties inherent in the sector so as to highlight the role of stakeholders such as investors, policymakers, project managers and contractors towards understanding dynamics driving various factors. Factors like corruption, fiscal policies, and institutional effectiveness play pivotal roles, with studies emphasizing the need for a nuanced understanding of these factors for sustainable growth. To be able to make informed decisions, formulate policies and achieve sustainable economic growth, it is important to unravel the secret drivers of money supply – GDP contribution interaction in Nigerian construction sector. As the industry evolves over time, impacted by macroeconomic changes and policies as well as internal dynamics reveals that an integrated approach based on continual adaptation responding to such challenges is needed.

References

- Adindu, C., Diugwu, I., Yusuf, S. and Musa, M. (2020) Issues of corruption in construction projects and infrastructure development in Nigeria: An empirical approach. *Supporting Inclusive Growth and Sustainable Development in Africa-Volume I: Sustainability in Infrastructure Development*, pp.191-200.
- Akaeze, N.S. and Akaeze, C. (2017) Exploring the survival strategies for small business ownership in Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(7), pp.35-48.
- Alaloul, W.S., Musarat, M.A., Rabbani, M.B.A., Iqbal, Q., Maqsoom, A. and Farooq, W. (2021) Construction sector contribution to economic stability: Malaysian GDP distribution. *Sustainability*, 13(9), p.5012.
- Areeb, Q.M., Nadeem, M., Sohail, S.S., Imam, R., Doctor, F., Himeur, Y., Hussain, A. and Amira, A. (2023) Filter bubbles in recommender systems: Fact or fallacy—A systematic review. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 13(6), p.e1512.
- Assa, J. (2016) *The Financialization of GDP: Implications for economic theory and policy*. Taylor & Francis.
- Babatunde, S.O., Awodele, O.A. and Adeniyi, O. (2018) Opportunities and challenges of foreign direct investment utilisation and its impact on construction sector in developing countries. *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction*, 23(2), pp.239-256.
- Bara, A. and Mudzingiri, C. (2016) Financial innovation and economic growth: evidence from Zimbabwe. *Investment management and financial innovations*, (13, Iss. 2), pp.65-75.
- Bergman, N. and Foxon, T.J. (2020) Reframing policy for the energy efficiency challenge: Insights from housing retrofits in the United Kingdom. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 63, p.101386.
- Brucker Juricic, B., Galic, M. and Marenjak, S. (2021) Review of the Construction Labour Demand and Shortages in the EU. *Buildings*, 11(1), p.17.
- Chan, A.P. and Owusu, E.K. (2022) Relational impacts of corruption on the procurement process: implications for economic growth in developing countries. In *Research Companion to Construction Economics* (pp. 466-490) Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Chiang, Y.H., Tao, L. and Wong, F.K. (2015) Causal relationship between construction activities, employment and GDP: The case of Hong Kong. *Habitat international*, 46, pp.1-12.
- Cornelissen, J.P., Durand, R., Fiss, P.C., Lammers, J.C. and Vaara, E. (2015) Putting communication front and center in institutional theory and analysis. *Academy of Management Review*, 40(1), pp.10-27.
- d'Agostino, G., Dunne, J.P. and Pieroni, L. (2016) Government spending, corruption and economic growth. *World Development*, 84, pp.190-205.
- David, P.A. (2014) The Republic of Open Science: The institution's historical origins and prospects for continued vitality
- Davis, G.F. and Kim, S. (2015) Financialization of the Economy. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 41, pp.203-221.
- El. seoud, M.S.A (2014), Testing the Relationship between Money Supply and GDP in Bahrain. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, 1(5):1-16.
- Fuenfschilling, L. and Truffer, B. (2014) The structuration of socio-technical regimes—Conceptual foundations from institutional theory. *Research policy*, 43(4), pp.772-791.
- Gomber, P., Kauffman, R.J., Parker, C. and Weber, B.W. (2018) On the fintech revolution: Interpreting the forces of innovation, disruption, and transformation in financial services. *Journal of management information systems*, 35(1), pp.220-265.
- Guobadia, J., Etim N. and Mfon, Ifiok (2024) The Impact of Monetary Policy Instruments on Nigeria's Construction Sector: A Focus on Money Supply, Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, and Interest Rate. *International Journal of Developmental Sustainable and environmental management* 4 (1) 1-15
- Guttman, R. (2017) Financialization revisited: the rise and fall of finance-led capitalism. *Economia e Societate*, 26, pp.857-877.
- Halcomb, E.J. and Hickman, L. (2015) Mixed methods research.
- Hampson, K.D., Kraatz, J.A. and Sanchez, A.X. (2014) The global construction industry and R&D. *R&D investment and impact in the global construction industry*, pp.42-61.

- Ifiok, Mfon., George, B. and Etim, N. (2024). Advancing Sustainability in Industrial Buildings: Materials and Construction Practices. *International Journal of Developmental Studies and Environmental Monitoring* 1(1) 1-7
- Khan, R.A., Liew, M.S. and Ghazali, Z.B. (2014) Malaysian construction sector and Malaysia vision 2020: Developed nation status. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 109, pp.507-513.
- Kipkirui, W.C. (2014) The effect of money supply on the gross domestic product in Kenya.
- Kolawole, A. (2015) Appraisal of the impact of corruption on sustainable development in Nigerian Construction Industry. *J. Multidiscip. Eng. Sci. Technol*, 2(10), pp.2834-2842.
- Lagos, R., Rocheteau, G. and Wright, R. (2014) The art of monetary theory: A new monetarist perspective. *Forthcoming, Journal of Economic Literature*.
- Langenwalter, G.A. (2020) *Enterprise resources planning and beyond: integrating your entire organization*. CRC Press.
- Larsen, J.K., Shen, G.Q., Lindhard, S.M. and Brunoe, T.D. (2016) Factors affecting schedule delay, cost overrun, and quality level in public construction projects. *Journal of management in engineering*, 32(1), p.04015032.
- Mfon, Ifiok (2023). Sustainable Materials and Construction Practices in Industrial Buildings. figshare. *Journal contribution*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24514870.v1>
- Molavi Vasséi, A. (2014) A Model of Monetarism. *Available at SSRN 2561575*.
- Morse, J.M. (2016) *Mixed method design: Principles and procedures* (Vol. 4) Routledge.
- Ngozi Eduzor. (2024). Leadership Styles and Organizational Performance: Examining the Impact of Transformational Leadership on Employee Engagement and Business Success. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 4 (1) pp 16-24
- Obstfeld, M. and Taylor, A.M. (2017) International monetary relations: Taking finance seriously. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(3), pp.3-28.
- Ogunmuyiwa M., and Francis E., (2010), Money Supply- Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria, *Olabisi Onabanjo University*, 22(3)
- Ojo, A.E., Ammasoma, D. and Adedokun, J.O. (2023) Responsiveness of the Construction Sector to Fiscal Policy in Nigeria. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 28(2), pp.121-137.
- Okafor, I.G., Ezeaku, H.C. and Ugwuegbe, U.S. (2016) Relationship between deposit money bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria under a VAR G-causality environment. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(2), pp.41-46.
- Oláh, J., Kitukutha, N., Haddad, H., Pakurár, M., Máté, D. and Popp, J. (2018) Achieving sustainable e-commerce in environmental, social and economic dimensions by taking possible trade-offs. *Sustainability*, 11(1), p.89.
- Olanipekun, A.O. and Saka, N. (2019) Response of the Nigerian construction sector to economic shocks. *Construction Economics and Building*, 19(2), pp.160-180.
- Oliva, F.L., Teberga, P.M.F., Testi, L.I.O., Kotabe, M., Del Giudice, M., Kelle, P. and Cunha, M.P. (2022) Risks and critical success factors in the internationalization of born global startups of industry 4.0: A social, environmental, economic, and institutional analysis. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, p.121346.
- Onat, N.C. and Kucukvar, M. (2020) Carbon footprint of construction industry: A global review and supply chain analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 124, p.109783.
- Peters, B.G. (2022) Institutional theory. In *Handbook on theories of governance* (pp. 323-335) Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Raymundo, R.B. (2017, June). Inefficiencies, disincentives and the misallocation of resources under the conditional cash transfer program. In *De La Salle University Research Congress, Manila, the Philippines*.

- Razzaq, A., Ajaz, T., Li, J.C., Irfan, M. and Suksatan, W. (2021) Investigating the asymmetric linkages between infrastructure development, green innovation, and consumption-based material footprint: Novel empirical estimations from highly resource-consuming economies. *Resources Policy*, 74, p.102302.
- Rigtering, J.C., Eggers, F., Kraus, S. and Chang, M.L. (2017) Entrepreneurial orientation, strategic planning and firm performance: The impact of national cultures. *European Journal of International Management*, 11(3), pp.301-324.
- Rüßmann, M., Lorenz, M., Gerbert, P., Waldner, M., Justus, J., Engel, P. and Harnisch, M. (2015) Industry 4.0: The future of productivity and growth in manufacturing industries. *Boston consulting group*, 9(1), pp.54-89.
- Sahoo, M. and Sethi, N. (2022) The dynamic impact of urbanization, structural transformation, and technological innovation on ecological footprint and PM2.5: evidence from newly industrialized countries. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(3), pp.4244-4277.
- Schoonenboom, J. and Johnson, R.B. (2017) How to construct a mixed methods research design. *Kolner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(Suppl 2), p.107.
- Schoonenboom, J. and Johnson, R.B. (2017) How to construct a mixed methods research design. *Kolner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(Suppl 2), p.107.
- Storm, S. (2018) Financialization and economic development: a debate on the social efficiency of modern finance. *Development and Change*, 49(2), pp.302-329.
- Sui Pheng, L., Shing Hou, L., Pheng, L.S. and Hou, L.S. (2019) The economy and the construction industry. *Construction Quality and the Economy: A Study at the Firm Level*, pp.21-54.
- Tengan, C., Oyewobi, L., Ogunbible, A. and Oke, A. (2016) Economic development as a function of construction project performance. *Journal of Construction Project Management and Innovation*, 6(2), pp.1447-1459.
- Timans, R., Wouters, P. and Heilbron, J. (2019) Mixed methods research: what it is and what it could be. *Theory and Society*, 48, pp.193-216.
- Toms, S., Wilson, N. and Wright, M. (2020) Innovation, intermediation, and the nature of entrepreneurship: A historical perspective. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 14(1), pp.105-121.
- Ugochukwu, S.C., Eze, G.C., Akabogu, S.C. and Abubakar, B.H. (2017) The correlation between foreign exchange rates and prices of building materials in Nigeria, 2011-2017) *The International Journal of Business & Management*.
- Wang, H., Lu, W., Söderlund, J. and Chen, K. (2018) The interplay between formal and informal institutions in projects: A social network analysis. *Project management journal*, 49(4), pp.20-35.
- Weimer, D. and Vining, A. (2017) *Policy analysis: Concepts and practice*. Routledge.
- Yap, J.B.H., Chow, I.N. and Shavarebi, K. (2019) Criticality of construction industry problems in developing countries: Analyzing Malaysian projects. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 35(5), p.04019020.
- Zaman, U., Florez-Perez, L., Abbasi, S., Nawaz, S., Farias, P. and Pradana, M. (2022) A stitch in time saves nine: nexus between critical delay factors, leadership self-efficacy, and transnational mega construction project success. *Sustainability*, 14(4), p.2091.
- Zhang, J., Chang, Y., Wang, C. and Zhang, L. (2018) The green efficiency of industrial sectors in China: A comparative analysis based on sectoral and supply-chain quantifications. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 132, pp.269-277.